

Policy Pathways for Marine Litter Prevention and Control: Insights from the SeaClear2.0 Project

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Introduction

Our oceans contain roughly 25 million tonnes of plastic waste. Over 90% of all marine litter is located on the seafloor, making it difficult and expensive to collect. While plastic pollution affects all waters across Europe, the Mediterranean is the most affected sea due to its semi-enclosed basin and the intense human activities taking place on the surrounding coastal areas. There is no one-size-fits-all approach to addressing marine litter. Concerted actions, combining legislation, technology and socio-economic tools are required to ensure that there is a paradigm shift in the way materials that end up as marine litter are produced, consumed and managed at the end of their life, and that “legacy” marine pollution is addressed.

The SeaClear2.0 project (www.seaclear2.eu) is developing an integrated approach to address the full cycle of marine litter in a way that will help meet the objectives of the European Union’s Mission to restore, protect and preserve the health of our oceans, seas and water by 2030. This approach includes the development of an autonomous team of robots that can detect and collect seabed and floating litter, and the development of recommendations for policy interventions that can help prevent and minimise marine litter as well as support technologies and innovations to restore affected areas and mitigate the impact of marine litter.

This paper presents an analysis of the policy framework that affects seabed marine litter (sources, prevention, collection, reuse/recycling) and relevant clean-up operations/technologies and identifies gaps, barriers, opportunities, synergies and coherence problems, both legal and institutional, at the EU and international level. It also makes recommendations that can help close regulatory gaps and loopholes, and take more concerted action to prevent and mitigate marine litter pollution.

Materials and methods

The policy analysis was conducted using a desk-study approach, analysing policies that can affect marine litter as well as policies influencing the development, uptake, and commercialization of the SeaClear2.0 innovations. A systematic approach was employed to identify, review, and analyse relevant policies (Figure 1). Initially, a broad spectrum of policies was identified, with a particular emphasis on those implemented at the European Union (EU) and international levels. To identify potential policies of relevance, keywords relevant to marine litter and technology were compiled. These keywords included ‘EU policy’, ‘EU law’, ‘waste’, ‘packaging’, ‘marine litter’, ‘plastics’, ‘artificial intelligence’, and ‘drones’, as well as combinations of these words.

Figure 1. The method used for the policy analysis.

The identified policies were subsequently screened based on their stated aims and objectives, and those deemed irrelevant to the focus areas were excluded from further consideration. For the remaining policies, the analysis sought to determine their potential to impact the generation of marine litter or the development, deployment, and commercialisation of systems such as SeaClear2.0. Specifically, the evaluation addressed how these policies could influence these areas positively or negatively and identified any barriers or opportunities they might present. A literature review, exploring themes of policy relevance and effectiveness, supplements the analysis.

Results and discussion

European policies that are relevant to marine litter, European policies that are relevant to the technical and/or commercial aspects of the innovations developed within the SeaClear2.0 project, and international policies relevant to marine litter were reviewed and analysed. The results demonstrate that the European and international policy framework on the issue of marine litter is comprehensive and evolving. Key policy recommendations stemming from the work fall within three broad categories: (i) design and prevention, (ii) waste management, (iii) marine litter, and (iv) technological innovation.

Design and prevention recommendations include (i) strengthening the focus on prevention, (ii) mandating the eco-design for plastics and polymers, (iii) accelerating the phase-out of harmful additives in plastics, (iv) expanding the bans on the destruction of unsold goods included in the Eco-design Regulation to include plastic-intensive product groups, (v) closing loopholes in the Single Use Plastics Directive and expanding its scope so that it is not limited to only plastic single-use products, (vi) mandating the reporting on the consumption of very lightweight plastic bags and heavyweight plastic bags and exploring relevant reduction targets, and (vii) supporting small and medium enterprises in adopting digital product passports.

Policy recommendations on waste management focus on (i) supporting a levelled circular economy approach across Europe by helping underperforming countries through capacity-building and financial support, (ii) addressing difficult-to-recycle plastics through investments in chemical recycling technologies, (iii) incentivizing investments in Europe's recycling infrastructure, (iv) curbing cigarette butt pollution as this remains an important problem which is unlikely to be resolved through extended producer responsibility alone, and (v) optimizing the management of ship-generated waste.

The recommendations that specifically address marine litter, with a focus on seabed litter, are: (i) improving data collection, sharing and interoperability through standardized data collection and sharing mechanisms as well as open-access, harmonized databases, (ii) mandating seabed litter monitoring and removal in European legislation, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, and (iii) tackling abandoned, lost or discarded fishing gear through the provision of appropriate and free-of-charge disposal facilities, investment in technologies and mechanisms for locating and removing lost gear, and research into fit-for-purpose alternative materials.

Finally, in terms of technological innovation two main policy recommendations emerge: (i) harmonizing cross-border regulation for autonomous marine technologies to facilitate innovation, cross-border collaboration and the widespread adoption of these technologies, and (ii) enabling SMEs and start-ups to scale innovative marine solutions through dedicated funding mechanisms and simplified regulatory pathways for testing and deployment.

Conclusions

Marine litter, particularly on the seafloor, remains a persistent and under-addressed challenge in European waters, requiring coordinated policy, innovation, and investment. While the EU has developed a comprehensive set of strategies and regulations, gaps in implementation, harmonisation, and enforcement limit their full effectiveness. Furthermore, real uptake of technological innovations to address marine litter, such as those developed by SeaClear2.0, depends on enabling policies, consistent funding mechanisms, and regulatory alignment across Member States. To ensure lasting impact, these efforts must be supported by inclusive, co-developed policy processes that translate ambition into action and empower both innovators and communities to be part of the solution. This paper has presented an initial set of policy recommendations towards this end, which will be discussed and validated through a high-level policy roundtable before being published in a White Paper.

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